

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Explicating Generative Artificial Intelligence Literacy of Management Students in India

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Abstract

Purpose: It is apparent that Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen-AI) is making its way into our daily lives. To navigate in an AI-influenced world and participate in future advances, students require a set of skills, known as AI Literacy, comprising using, applying, and communicating with AI. The current work discusses the future managers' ability to understand and critically use Gen AI technologies with an emphasis on their technological, ethical, and socio-organizational dimensions. This literacy development is critical to students' academic performance and their future success in the AI-enabled workplace. This paper's objective is to assess the depth and quality of Gen-AI literacy among management students in India and find out whether demographic groups are comparable by level of GenAI literacy.

Methodology: We used a quantitative cross-sectional design. Data were collected from management students from various Indian states through a questionnaire developed based on an established AI literacy scale. The scale successfully captured 6 dimensions of Gen-AI literacy: the social impact, execution, problem solving with Gen-AI, data literacy and AI ethics.

Results: The findings reveal a moderate level of Gen-AI competency in management students. Respondents demonstrated greater awareness of social and ethical considerations, but less proficiency in problem-solving with Gen-AI software. No significant differences existed in Gen-AI proficiency by gender, family income, the background of parents or prior academic stream.

Originality/Value: This study contributes to the growing domain of Gen-AI by evaluating the AI literacy of management students and supporting for improvement of students' AI literacy levels. The present study achieved greater results by combining several methodological strengths, addressing persistent limitations in GenAI literacy research, and focusing on an underrepresented population.

Keywords: AI Literacy; Generative AI; Literacy Assessment; Students' Literacy; Management

1 Introduction

The digital technologies have evolved over the period of time and marked transformational phase as ‘The rise of generative AI systems.’ On the basis of this, Gen-AI is one of the fastest-moving areas of advancement in computing, featuring algorithms with the ability to create new content by learning and mimicking complex patterns of data. Its expanding capabilities have begun influencing numerous domains from communication to creative industries. However, this growth comes with a dual character: while the technology opens up unprecedented creative possibilities, it also raises difficult ethical, social, and philosophical questions that continue to challenge researchers and practitioners alike⁽¹⁾.

As generative AI continues to reshape technological landscapes, the idea of Gen-AI literacy has become central in understanding this shift. Rather than referring merely to technical proficiency or routine computer skills, Gen-AI literacy involves a broader capability, i.e., the ability to interpret, question, and purposefully use generative systems in various contexts. This competency influences not only how individuals interact with emerging tools but also how communities adapt to the changing dynamics of digital creation and decision-making. Without such understanding, the rapid evolution of these tools can outpace users’ capacity to evaluate their implications or apply them responsibly.

Gen-AI literacy refers to the capacity, knowledge, and understanding individuals possess to engage, comprehend, and responsibly utilize generative AI⁽²⁾. At its core, as shown in Figure 1, AI encompasses a spectrum of competencies, from the foundational understanding of how Gen-AI functions to the critical appraisal of its ethical, societal, and cultural implications.

This research paper explores the understanding of Gen-AI among college students. It looks at how different factors, like age and background, can influence this understanding. The goal of the study is to help students develop a deeper knowledge of Gen-AI technologies and learn how to use them responsibly. By doing so, it aims to support students’ overall growth and development.

In doing so, we aspire to contribute to the ongoing discourse surrounding AI ethics, education, and societal implications, thereby paving the way for informed discourse and judicious integration of Gen-AI into our academic curriculum.

Since Gen-AI literacy is new research domain and literature has just started growing, we have to take base of traditional-AI literacy research studies published in recent years. This literature reviews amalgamate insights from a plethora of research endeavors aimed at conceptualizing, assessing, and fostering AI literacy across various demographic segments.

2 Review of Literature

2.1 Conceptualization and dimensions of AI Literacy

The ability to comprehend the fundamental methods and ideas underlying artificial intelligence (AI) in various goods and services was defined as AI literacy^{(3), (4), (5)}. Furthermore, multiple studies link AI literacy to perceived ability, confidence, and eagerness to study AI.

In order to define AI literacy, previous researchers⁽⁶⁾ give an exploratory review that culminates in four essential components: know and comprehend, use and apply, assess and develop, and ethical issues. The review suggests a foundational framework, which is based on 30 published peer-reviewed articles, the review enlightens further research and shapes the conversation about AI literacy⁽⁶⁾.

Various studies delineate multifaceted dimensions of AI literacy^{(7), (8), (9)}. From technology-related competencies to ethical considerations, the construct spans understanding AI processes, ethical implications, operational skills, and socio-technical competencies^{(7), (8), (9)}.

A researcher⁽⁷⁾ investigated the meaning of employees’ know-how of AI in existing literature using a bibliometrics analyzing 250+ articles⁽⁷⁾. The findings emphasize four categories of AI literacy capabilities related to, namely technology, work, humanizing, and learning abilities, emphasizing the significance of operationalizing AI literacy for non-AI professionals.

According to a study, awareness, use, evaluation, and ethics are the main fundamental constructs of AI literacy⁽⁸⁾. Variables like ‘Digital literacy’, ‘Attitudes toward robots’, and users’ ‘Everyday use of AI’ are all strongly correlated with AI literacy. A study created a testing tool to assess middle school children’s AI literacy⁽¹⁰⁾. The domains include data literacy, AI ethics, problem solving with AI, AI execution strategies, and the social impact of AI.

2.2 Determinants and Influencing Factors

It is essential that individuals, regardless of their age or academic background to have a know-how of AI^{(11), (12), (13)}. Laupichler⁽¹¹⁾ highlighted how crucial it is for both children and adults to be introduced to AI concepts at an early age. This early exposure not only fosters a fundamental understanding of technology but also helps demystify AI, making it more accessible and relatable. On the other hand, Kong⁽¹²⁾ demonstrated that teaching AI literacy courses to university students from various

disciplines regardless of their programming backgrounds can be both practical and effective. This approach opens doors for students from different fields to engage with AI in a meaningful way, allowing them to incorporate these essential skills into their future careers. It's exciting to think about how such initiatives can empower a diverse range of individuals to navigate and thrive in an increasingly tech-driven world. In order to equip middle school teenagers with the fundamental knowledge and abilities necessary to support their future endeavors as AI-empowered professionals, researchers created an AI workshop that would help them become rational-thinking citizens and astute AI technology users⁽¹³⁾.

The authors conducted the study to design, implement, and evaluate an AI literacy course for university students⁽¹²⁾. One of the research topics was if a literacy course could assist college students from many fields in cultivating a conceptual knowledge of AI. The results showed that people of different genders and study backgrounds could understand topics like ML, supervised and unsupervised learning, regression, classification, and clustering. People who learned about AI principles didn't need to know how to program before, and the flipped classroom method provided them more freedom in how they learned.

Researchers pinpointed cognitive absorption, computational thinking, the digital divide, and ICT availability as key factors affecting AI literacy⁽¹⁴⁾. The suggested model highlights how cognitive factors, access to technology, and personal motivation all interact to shape a person's AI literacy. It's interesting to see how these elements come together. For instance, individuals with a strong motivation to learn and a good grasp of AI tools tend to achieve better results. When someone feels excited about using technology and knows how to navigate it effectively, they are more likely to succeed and thrive in this digital age. Ultimately, AI literacy is not just about knowledge; it's about embracing the tools at our disposal and being eager to grow.

A number of recent studies expand the discourse beyond fundamental AI literacy^{(11), (15)}. They go into further detail about higher-order psychological skills that are important in a time when AI systems are everywhere, focusing on AI self-efficacy, self-management, and creative potential.

2.3 Assessment and Measurement of AI literacy

Numerous efforts focus on assessing AI literacy. For example, instruments for middle school students⁽¹⁰⁾ or the evaluation framework⁽⁸⁾ for junior high school students and Library and Information Science students showcase the diversity of assessment tools tailored to specific demographics and cultural contexts⁽¹⁶⁾.

Researchers examine junior high school students' AI literacy in China and create the framework for evaluating AI literacy in junior high schools⁽⁸⁾. The evaluation's findings indicate that while students' AI literacy is generally excellent, there is unequal improvement in four areas. Junior middle school kids' AI literacy varies significantly depending on their sex, academic grade, class routine, task collaboration frequency, learning value and objective, and self-confidence.

To increase the efficacy of class instruction and the uptake of AI literacy, researchers investigated the relationships between the various aspects of teachers' AI literacy⁽¹⁷⁾. The results were derived from an examination of 1013 survey responses, in which researchers assessed instructors' AI literacy in terms of Knowing and Comprehending AI, Utilizing AI, Evaluating AI Application, and AI Morality.

A study sought to investigate the connections between Chinese secondary school students' ways to learning AI, their AI literacy, and their computational thinking efficacy in learning AI⁽¹⁸⁾. The results showed that students' computational thinking efficacy in learning AI was positively correlated with AI literacy, which was mediated by more sophisticated methods of learning AI, adding to our current understanding of learning AI.

An item set for evaluating non-experts' AI literacy using the Delphi technique was presented in a prior study⁽¹¹⁾. According to experts, there aren't many elements on the measure that assess knowledge or comprehension of AI and attitudes toward it⁽⁸⁾.

Researchers created a method to measure AI literacy by looking at the parts "Embrace & Implement AI," "Understand AI," "Detecting AI," and "AI Morality." They also looked at "Create AI" as a distinct part, "AI Self-efficacy in learning and problem solving," and "AI Self-management"⁽¹⁵⁾. Higher-order psychological skills are also covered, which are crucial given the widespread transformation brought about by AI systems.

Recent studies highlight growing AI integration in higher education, showing benefits for engagement, writing, and conceptual learning^{(19), (20)}. Research also identifies institutional challenges like limited faculty readiness, curriculum gaps, and technology access. Studies reveal uneven AI literacy and confidence among students^{(16), (21)}.

2.4 Research Gap

The literature on generative AI for AI literacy is lacking as discussed in Table 1.

Gen-AI literacy lacks affluent literature on dimensions, assessment tools, influencing factors, and educational strategies. This study assesses Gen-AI literacy among Indian university students, filling a research gap. After Industry 6.0, Gen-AI literacy must be researched and integrated into educational curriculum.

Table 1. Research gaps motivating the current investigation.

Research Aspect	Prior Studies (Examples)	Rationale for Current Study
Data Type	Secondary data, bibliometric reviews, exploratory research, qualitative interviews. ^{(3), (22), (23), (24)}	Need to work on primary data to establish baseline GenAI competence levels in underrepresented contexts.
Statistical Analysis	Descriptive only; no inferential tests ⁽³⁾	Requires testing demographic influences to validate equity claims in AI literacy literature.
Study Design	Cross-sectional study; no longitudinal tracking	Establishes cross-sectional benchmark as foundation for tracking GenAI skill evolution.
Measurement Tool	Narrow scales (missing ethics/data domains)	Demands comprehensive, validated and reliable measurement instrument.
Geographic Focus	More focus on Western and region-specific sample	Aims to fulfil critical gap of quantitative assessment of GenAI competence data from Indian management students.
Student Group	General/mixed disciplines (Library and information science, K-12)	Justifies isolating management students because this discipline students represents key future workforce for AI-driven business decisions.
Key competences Covered	Fragmented domains such as ethics OR technical OR social. Previous studies rarely presented comprehensive viewpoint.	Calls for integrated assessment of technical understanding + ethical reasoning + real-world application

This study also investigates demographic factors and Gen-AI literacy from an interdisciplinary perspective. This study clarifies how to develop a sophisticated understanding and responsible use of Gen-AI technology to support the Indian government's goal of holistic development of students.

2.5 Research Objectives

The fast growth of generative AI (Gen-AI) in business functions necessitates an assessment of how ready students are to integrate these technologies. Despite increasing debates on AI literacy, empirical-based evidence of Gen-AI literacy among developing-economy students (especially in management career) remains scarce and lacking for that matter with the utilization of exhaustive multidimensional measurement frameworks. Therefore, this study aims:

- To ascertain the level of Generative AI literacy among management students in India, using a multidimensional grid of literacy that includes knowledge related to technical, application proficiency and ethical precautions, data literacies and perceived social impact.
- To investigate how the perception of Gen-AI literacy is different through selected demographic variables such as gender, previous education stream, family income, and father and mother's education/occupation.
- To understand the opportunities and challenges related to different dimensions of Gen-AI literacy so as to inform the development of curricula and pedagogical interventions in management education.

In pursuing these objectives, this research paper seeks to set a benchmark for Gen-AI literacy for Indian management students and contribute to the relatively scant literature on Gen-AI readiness in non-technical community institutions of higher education.

2.6 Conceptual Framework

The current research contributes to the multidimensional conceptualization of Generative Artificial Intelligence (Gen-AI) literacy which views AI literacy as a multi-faceted competence rather than a technical skill. Figure 1 reveals that the model represents AI Literacy as a foundational construct underpinned by four overlapping competencies domains: Technical Knowledge, Critical Evaluation, Ethical Awareness and Adaptation/Innovation which in turn are bolstered by communication and learning skills.

The students' technical expertise enables them to appropriately interact with AI tools, interpret results, and understand the opportunities and limitations of AI systems. Critical evaluation, in this sense, acts as a safeguard against the uncritical use of generative systems and serves to provide guidance when making decisions professionally or academically.

AI Literacy Framework: Key Components and Skills

Fig 1. A spectrum of competencies for Generative AI literacy.

The Ethical Component is a core part of the framework and mirrors a growing emphasis on ethical use of AI. This is the capacity to recognize ethical concerns around Gen-AI. These concerns revolve around data bias, content misuse, privacy threats and societal isolation. Students’ ethical awareness helps them not just understand the potential of AI, but also consider ethical, legal and societal aspects of working with AI-generated outputs in corporate and business contexts.

Adaptability and Innovation are associated with the ability to creatively employ Gen-AI tools in a dynamic context. This skill is particularly critical for students of management because it facilitates strategic thinking process to support strategy formation and creative decision making in AI augmented workplace. It offers theoretical grounds for investigating the disparate perceptions of Gen-AI literacy.

By operationalizing Gen-AI literacy in this model, the paper extends notions of technical literacy and outlines the cognitive, ethical evaluative and adaptive skills that are necessary for individuals to be able to make use of Generative AI technologies effectively as well as responsibly in management education and beyond.

3 Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This research adopts a cross-sectional, quantitative survey methodology which appropriate to access GenAI literacy of Management students of India. The study adopts a self-assessment tool to collect student's perception of their GenAI know-how. Survey is selected as a method to obtain feedback on account of the exploratory character of Gen AI literacy research and scarcity of empirical scale in this dimension. The purpose of this study is to evaluate GenAI literacy on below-mentioned six dimensions to support policy making and advance academic curriculum development.

3.2 Sample and process

The students of management stream formed the universe of the study as these future managers and leaders are expected to leverage Gen-AI for innovative strategies, data-driven decisions, and creative problem-solving, fostering competitive edge in a technology-driven business landscape. Therefore, the data were collected from 182 graduation and postgraduate students of the management department. These students got admission after clearing national level entrance test, thus, possess satisfactory intellect and caliber. These university students belonged to the various cities of Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, Uttar Pradesh, Bihar, Rajasthan, etc. While it is not generalizable to the whole country, the sample certainly consists of enough social and economic diversity at a national level for an exploratory statistical study.

3.3 Measurement scale

To examine the level of Gen-AI literacy, there is no measurement scale available, therefore a questionnaire designed by Kim and Lee⁽¹⁰⁾ based on Traditional-AI literacy was used and modified to suit the context. There were two sections to the questionnaire. First section included Six domains which are: the social impact of AI (eight questions), understanding of AI (six questions), AI execution plans (five questions), problem solving with AI (five questions), data literacy (four questions), and AI ethics (two questions), which focused on the respondents' perceived literacy level (Table 2). The second part linked Gen-AI literacy level with demographic variables. The survey was conducted online in English using the Qualtrics Survey. The participants provided their informed consent after being made aware of the study's overall goal.

3.4 Data Collection Procedure

This study employed an online survey, which was distributed by means of Qualtrics Software. The mode of administration online was selected in order to maximize the survey reach and convenience for participants. Before participating, respondents were provided with information about the goals of the study, assurance of anonymity, and obtained informed consent. The survey was administered for a predetermined amount of time. Inconsistent responses were excluded from the analysis in order to have good quality data.

3.5 Hypotheses Development and Rationale

Research on AI literacy has shown contradictory trends relating to the role of demographic variables such as gender, socio-economic conditions or access to education. While there is some evidence of inequalities for access and prior experience, the impact of demographics appears to decrease in more digitally intensive educational contexts. However, few recent studies based in developing countries have shown demographic differences⁽⁸⁾.

The alternate hypotheses to understand demographic differences are:

H1: There is a significant difference between the perceived Gen-AI literacy of the students with respect to their gender.

H2: There is a significant difference among the perceived Gen-AI literacy of the students with respect to their family income.

H3: There is a significant difference among the perceived Gen-AI literacy of the students with respect to their prior education stream.

H4: There is a significant difference among the perceived Gen-AI literacy of the students with respect to occupation of their parents.

3.6 Analysis tools

Descriptive analysis is performed to assess and present the AI literacy of students. An independent sample t-test was used to find out if there was a statistically significant difference between the students' AI literacy skills based on their gender. A one-way

Table 2. Measurement scale developed by Kim and Lee⁽¹⁰⁾.

Social impact of AI Item 8	1.	I can ethically judge the results or actions produced by artificial intelligence.
	2.	I can explain the impact artificial intelligence will have on privacy.
	3.	I can talk about the impact artificial intelligence will have on future jobs.
	4.	I can predict how jobs will change with the advancement of artificial intelligence.
	5.	I can predict how our lives will change through artificial intelligence.
	6.	I can predict what artificial intelligence will be able to do in the future.
	7.	I can talk about the potential impact of artificial intelligence on our society.
	8.	I can explain the difference between current artificial intelligence and future artificial intelligence.
The understanding of AI Item 5	9.	I can develop a plan to successfully execute an artificial intelligence project.
	10.	I know all the information necessary to proceed with an artificial intelligence project.
	11.	I can produce solutions to problems that arise during the process of carrying out an artificial intelligence project.
	12.	I can use my artificial intelligence knowledge in artificial intelligence projects.
	13.	I can lead artificial intelligence project
AI execution plans item 5	14.	I can use artificial intelligence to get the results I need.
	15.	I can distinguish between problems that can be solved with artificial intelligence and problems that cannot be solved.
	16.	I can talk about the advantages and disadvantages of the problem-solving process using artificial intelligence.
	17.	I can select an appropriate model to solve problems through artificial intelligence.
	18.	I can test the accuracy of the artificial intelligence program I created.
Problem solving AI item 6	19.	I can explain the process by which artificial intelligence produces results.
	20.	I know how artificial intelligence recognizes the real world (pictures, language, etc.).
	21.	I can explain the changes that occur when artificial intelligence is introduced in technology.
	22.	I can simplify and explain the operating principles of artificial intelligence.
	23.	I can explain the principles by which artificial intelligence classifies images (e.g., dogs and cats, numbers).
	24.	I can talk about ways for artificial intelligence to increase the accuracy or speed of image discrimination.
	25.	I know what data is needed to successfully carry out an artificial intelligence project.
Data literacy item 4	26.	I can process, transform, organize, and analyze data to suit the needs of the situation.
	27.	I can use data for learning, decision making, and problem solving.
	28.	I can critically evaluate data content and sources.
AI ethics item 2	29.	I can collect data from diverse perspectives rather than biased data.
	30.	I can suggest ways to properly utilize artificial intelligence socially.

ANOVA was conducted to ascertain the differences in the students' AI literacy levels, based upon their prior education stream, family's monthly income, the educational qualification of father and mother and occupation of their father and mother. The variable age was excluded from our study since all of the students were in the same age range, which is between 18 and 24.

4 Result and Discussion

4.1 Demographic analysis

Table 3 shows that out of 182 respondents, there is fair distribution of sample regarding gender, that is, 53% respondents identified as male. The prior education stream of most of the respondents was from management/commerce, which is 53.8% respondents. The majority of responders came from households that earned more than Rs. 50,000 a month. The respondents' parents were identified to be educated. Regarding fathers' occupations, 53% of respondents stated that their fathers work as businessmen, while the remaining respondents said that their fathers are in service. Mothers were described as housewives by 57.7% of respondents and as servicewomen by 24.2% of respondents.

Table 3. Demographic Profile of the Students.

Demographic Variables	Categories	Absolute Figure	Percentage
Gender	Male	98	53.8
	Female	84	46.2
Family Monthly Income	Below Rs. 50,000	19	10.4
	‘ 50,000–100,000	48	26.4
	‘ 100,000–150,000	54	29.7
	Above 150,000	61	33.5
Prior education stream	Commerce/Management	98	53.8
	Mass communication	2	1.1
	Art	8	4.4
	Science	74	40.7
Father’s Qualification	High School	19	10.4
	Graduate	68	37.4
	Postgraduate	81	44.5
	Any other	14	7.7
Mother’s Qualification	High School	24	13.2
	Graduate	73	40.1
	Postgraduate	55	30.2
Father’s Occupation	Any other	30	16.5
	Businessman	98	53.8
	Serviceman	84	46.2
	Any other	0	0.0
Mother’s Occupation	Businesswoman	33	18.1
	Servicewoman	44	24.2
	Any other	105	57.7

4.2 AI-literacy assessment

The results (Table 4) showed that respondents were 65.59% confident on their Gen-AI literacy. Students scored low on “understanding of AI” and “problem solving with AI”, which is supported by Previous researchers who documented confidence issues and limitations among business and LIS students in South Asia and globally^{(16), (21)}. Notably, students moderately understand the Social impact and ethical aspects of AI.

Table 4. Responses to Gen-AI literacy questions.

Variable	Average Score out of 5	Support from literature
Social impact of Gen-AI	3.56	(1)
The understanding of Gen-AI	2.9	(16), (21)
Gen-AI execution plans	3.307	–
Problem solving Gen-AI	3.093	(16), (21)
Data literacy	3.343	–
Gen-AI ethics	3.494	(2)

4.3 Hypothesis testing

The t-test was performed to discover if there were any significant gender-based disparities in the pupils’ Gen-AI literacy. The t-test’s level of significance is 0.830. Since this value is higher than 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted and there is no discernible gender difference in university students’ Gen-AI literacy⁽¹²⁾. It can be inferred that there is no difference in the Gen-AI literacy levels of male and female students because they study the same curriculum.

In order to determine whether significant differences exist in the Gen-AI literacy levels of the students on the basis of their prior education stream, family's monthly income, the educational qualification of father and mother and occupation of their father and mother, one-way ANOVA was applied. Because all of the p-values in Table 5 are greater than 0.05, we accept the null hypotheses. This means that there is no significant difference in the Gen-AI literacy of university students based on the characteristics listed above. Income and parental background variables have not been strongly evidenced in literature as modifiers for AI literacy outcomes, underscoring the study's unique contribution.

Table 5. Summary of one-way ANOVA.

Demographic Variables		DF	Mean Square	F	P-value
Family Monthly Income	Between Groups	3	1,260.72	2.139	0.12
	Within Groups	181	589.781		
	Total	184			
Prior education stream	Between Groups	3	1,246.02	2.135	0.10
	Within Groups	181	583.754		
	Total	184			
Father's Qualification	Between Groups	3	80.853	0.132	0.94
	Within Groups	181	617.364		
	Total	184			
Mother's Qualification	Between Groups	3	1,106.06	1.883	0.14
	Within Groups	181	587.791		
	Total	184			
Father's Occupation	Between Groups	3	1,338.78	2.34	0.08
	Within Groups	181	581.078		
	Total	184			
Mother's Occupation	Between Groups	3	389.058	0.631	0.59
	Within Groups	181	608.474		
	Total	184			

Prior works were critiqued for limited psychometric evidence, lack of cross-cultural validity, and rare focus on generative AI skills rather than general AI literacy. The present study achieved better results than many previously reported works by combining several methodological strengths, addressing persistent limitations in generative AI literacy research, and focusing on an underrepresented population. In this study, we use a unique instrument that focuses on multiple important aspects: social impact, ethics, data literacy, application, and understanding. These dimensions are often overlooked or addressed in isolation in many advanced techniques and existing scales, e.g. MAILS and GLAT⁽⁵⁾, (25).

5 Conclusion

The present research addressed a gap in the literature by examining generative AI (Gen-AI) literacy among management students in India, a group that has received limited attention. Responses from student participants revealed a reasonably great self-confidence level in their Gen-AI abilities (65.59%). Students showed a better understanding of the ethical and social implications of AI, however, their grasp of technical concepts and problem-solving tasks was weaker. The study found that perceived Gen-AI literacy levels were relatively high, yet unaffected by demographic variables.

An additional contribution of this work lies in its exploration of demographic influences. Factors such as gender, academic specialization, household income, and parental education were considered, yet none of these variables showed meaningful differences in literacy outcomes. This pattern suggests that, within this sample, generative AI awareness and confidence may be relatively uniform across diverse student backgrounds. This study's use of the standardized AI literacy scale, which includes data literacy, ethics, and application, provides content validity as a strength. This comprehensive approach improves measurement accuracy and depth. Additionally, studying Indian management students fills a gap in cross-cultural AI literacy research.

This study improves the measurement and context of generative AI literacy, laying the groundwork for curriculum and policy changes to prepare students for AI-driven workplaces. The study aids researchers in understanding user competency in AI technology and helps developers create applications that match users' literacy levels.

6 Limitations and Recommendations for Future Research, Contributions to Practice

6.1 Limitations of the Study

Despite its value in the field, there are several limitations to be acknowledged when interpreting the results of this present research.

- The study is cross-sectional to a certain extent, examining Gen-AI literacy at one point in time. Due to the fast pace of advance related to Generative AI tools and their integration in educational applications that paradigm might be going to change quickly. A snapshot picture can also hardly be illustrative of learning trajectories and skill development, nor could it depict long-term effects on curricula exposure to Gen AI.
- The proposed study relies on self-reported Gen-AI literacy of the participants, as opposed to their actual performance on tested tasks. Although perceived competence is an important psychological variable, it may not accurately correspond to the ability of handling or evaluating generative AI technology or dealing with the problems that arise from such a tool in practice. Overconfidence and social desirability bias could be another explanation, which may have caused the respondents to give an inflated rating.
- This study has some limitations on part of institutional comparisons and limited demographic factors, thus, providing opportunities for further exploration.

These limitations highlight priority areas for targeted educational interventions in AI literacy development.

6.2 Recommendations for Future Research

Based on the results and limitations, several research directions for future investigation are proposed.

- Further studies are warranted to use longitudinal research designs in order to assess the development over time of Gen-AI literacy, notably before and after participants' experiences with formal AI-related workshops, courses or other experiential components. Such designs might contribute to increasing our understanding of the learning process and skill retention.
- It is recommended to add performance-based assessment in self-report measures of research. While there are simulations, cases or scenarios using AI tools online that could potentially give students simulated real-time feedback on their skills.
- External validity can be strengthened by expanding research to larger more diverse sample sizes at institutions, in regions and among academic levels. Research that compares between countries or developed and developing states would also allow context-specific differences in Gen-AI literacy to be illuminated.
- In addition, further analyses will have to be conducted concerning the pedagogical and institutional learning contexts that shape Gen-AI Literacy, such as, accessibility of AI tools to faculty at an institution and students' actual frequency and motivation of use of Gen-AI.

6.3 Contribution to Practice

This research provides many valuable implications for education and policy practices, and curriculum development particularly in management education.

- The findings help to empirically evidence the present Gen-AI literacy of Indian students of management. This information will enable universities and business schools to determine precise gaps in student ability, particularly, about problem-solving and technical knowledge using Gen-AI as opposed to assuming the digital skills of students.
- The multifaceted assessment model used in this study demonstrates the importance of balanced AI education. The comparatively much higher performance in social and ethical aspects as opposed to a more technical knowledge, imply that the curricula should advance from awareness-building discourses onto practical learning.
- A low variation across the demographics also means that Gen-AI literacy interventions can be general and there is no need of building in hefty demographic-specific customizations. The emphasis of institutions should be on curriculum reorganization across all schools rather than remediation for some students.
- The research also supports organizational wisdom and formal integration of Gen-AI literacy into the curriculum of management education in India.

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